

Measurement of Micro-cataphoretic Velocity of Particles of Zinc Ferrocyanide Sol with Correction for Surface-Conductance Effect

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The electrophoretic mobility (U_a) of particles of Zinc ferrocyanide sol has been measured in presence of equicoagulating concentrations of electrolytes. Attempt has been made to apply correction for surface conductance on the basis of the equations:

$$\frac{1}{U_a} = \frac{1}{U} + \frac{m}{S} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{1}{U_a} = \frac{1}{U} + \frac{M}{\sqrt{V}} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

in equation (1) S represents the bulk specific conductance and $m = \kappa/UR$, κ being the specific surface conductance, R , the radius of an insulating particle and U , the electrophoretic mobility corrected for surface conductance effect; in equation (2) M represents $\kappa/S \cdot U \cdot R$ and $R = K \sqrt{V}$, V being the velocity of sedimentation of a colloidal particle. The corrected electrophoretic mobility (U) found on the basis of equation (1) is 2.25×10^{-4} cm/sec/volt/cm and that found on the basis of equation (2) is 2.23×10^{-4} cm/sec/volt/cm.

On account of ion-relaxation¹⁻², surface conductance³⁻⁵, and also electro-viscous⁶ effects, the zeta-potential of a colloidal system, when calculated with the help of Smoluchowski equation $\zeta = \frac{4\pi\eta}{D} \cdot U$ (where η , the coefficient of viscosity, D , the dielectric constant of the medium, and U , the electrophoretic mobility of an insulating particle) may not represent its true value. For electrophoresis of an insulating particle of large kR where k is the characteristic term of the Debye-Hückel equation and R , the radius of a particle, the equation of Henry and Booth may be expressed as

$$\frac{1}{U_a} = \frac{1}{U} + \frac{m}{S} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where U_a and U represent observed and true electrophoretic mobility, S , the bulk specific conductance and m is a constant and is equal to κ/UR where, κ is the specific surface conductance.

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Again, applying Stoke's law for the particles of a sol suspended in a solution of an electrolyte of desired concentration and also at a definite temperature,

$$R = K\sqrt{V}$$

where K is a constant and V is the velocity of sedimentation. For a given concentration of an electrolyte, κ , U and S remain constant and so equation (1) may be written as

$$\frac{1}{U_s} = \frac{1}{U} + \frac{M}{\sqrt{V}} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

The present investigation has been undertaken using a more or less pure sol of zinc ferrocyanide with a view to ascertain the value of its electrophoretic mobility, corrected for surface conductance, using equations (1) and (2) separately. It is obvious from these two equations that a linearity between the values of $1/U_s$ vs. $1/S$ or $1/\sqrt{v}$ should hold good.

EXPERIMENTAL

To a $M/10$ solution of $ZnSO_4$ (E. Merck) was added an $M/15$ solution of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ (E. Merck) with constant stirring until the precipitation was complete. At this stage, the whole of the precipitate was shaken vigorously with conductivity water to which a small amount of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ was added as a peptising agent. The sol thus prepared was purified by dialysis in cellophane bags and allowed to age for one week. The white coloured sol was found to be negatively charged having specific conductance 1.82×10^{-4} ohm $^{-1}$ cm $^{-1}$ and pH 6.62 at 25°.

A weighed quantity of purified and dried coagulum was digested with H_2SO_4 (conc.). The final volume of the solution was made upto 250 ml. An aliquot portion of the solution was pipetted and analysed for Zn, Fe, and N. From the analytical data the composition of the sol appears to be $K_2Zn_3 [Fe(CN)_6]_4$.

Equicoagulating concentrations of different Electrolytes.—The equicoagulating concentrations were determined for KCl, $MgSO_4$, $MgCl_2$, $La(NO_3)_3$ and also for their mixtures in the zone of slow coagulation (15 min.) in a manner described previously⁹. The data are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I
Time = 15 min. + 2 min. centrifuging at 2000 r.p.m.

Coagulant	Final conc. of the electrolyte $C \times 10^3$ (M)		
KCl	316.5 ^a	*308.3 ^b	300.1 ^c
$MgSO_4$	3.91 ^a	*3.78 ^b	3.64 ^c
$MgCl_2$	3.16 ^a	*3.08 ^b	3.00 ^c
$La(NO_3)_3$	0.106 ^a	*0.104 ^b	0.1024 ^c
KCl $La(NO_3)_3$	(2.06+0.086) ^a	*(2.06+0.083) ^b	(2.06+0.081) ^c
Do	(1.03+0.094) ^a	*(1.03+0.092) ^b	(1.03+0.09) ^c
Do	(0.26+0.101) ^a	*(0.26+0.099) ^b	(0.26+0.097) ^c

*denotes equicoagulating concentration.

a,b,c, denote respectively clear, just clear and slightly turbid.

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Measurement of Mobility.—The electrophoretic mobility, U_e , of the particles was measured by the microcataphoretic method. The microcataphoretic cell used was of the Abramson modification of the original Northrop-Kunitz type flat cell. According to a previous arrangement¹⁰, the plane of the cell was placed vertically and the axis of the microscope horizontally. The microscope with which the particles were observed in the cell was fitted with a scale having squares etched on it in the eye piece. With a view to measuring mobilities of the particles having different radii, the electrolyte selected was $MgSO_4$ at the equicoagulating concentration. A definite volume of the colloid was mixed with an equal volume of the electrolyte and centrifuged after 15 min. A little of the coagula thus separating was then taken with the supernatant liquid to form a suspension containing particles of different sizes inside the cell. A particle in the field of vision was selected and allowed to sediment. The time taken to fall through a given distance by the particle was noted. Then by applying current, the velocity of the same particle was noted. In this manner, the velocity of sedimentation and mobility of a number of particles were determined. The technique adopted for measuring the variation of U_e with S was a little different as described so far. The particles having the same rate of fall in the microcataphoretic cell were selected and their mobilities were determined for different electrolytes at their respective equicoagulating concentrations.

All the experiments were carried out at 25°C and for conductance measurement a Philips PR 9500 bridge was employed.

DISCUSSION

It is evident from Table I that the equicoagulating concentrations of the electrolytes, which coagulate the Zinc ferrocyanide sol in 15 mins., are in accordance with the valency rule of Schulze and Hardy. Their ratio, when expressed in millimoles per litre, is as $KCl : MgCl_2 : MgSO_4 : La(NO_3)_3 : 100 : 0.9991 : 1.225 : 0.0338$; where this ratio is compared

with the inverse sixth power rule (mono: di: tri: 100: 1.6 : 0.13). The agreement between KCl and MgSO_4 is found to be satisfactory. The deviation in the observed value of $\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ is probably due to its hydrolysis.

TABLE-II

(Refer to Fig. 2)

Data on observed electrophoretic mobility U_a and bulk Sp. Cond., S ,Temp. = 25° $m = x/ur. = 0.45$ Corrected electrophoretic mobility (U) = 2.25×10^{-4} cm/sec/volt/cm.

Electrolytes	Equicoagulating conc. (C) ($C \times 10^4 M$)	pH of the supernatant liquid	Obs. mobility (U_a)* ($U_a \times 10^4$)	Sp. cond (S)* ($S \times 10^3$)
MgSO_4	37.76	6.50	2.02	0.8139
MgCl_2	30.80	6.92	2.00	0.7608
KCl	20.55			
+	+	6.46	1.87	0.4269
$\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3$	0.84			
KCl	10.28			
+	+	6.46	1.50	0.2857
$\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3$	0.9173			
KCl	2.569			
+	+	6.48	1.43	0.1768
$\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3$	0.9902			
$\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3$	1.042	6.48	1.23	0.1294

*In cm/sec./volt/cm.

†In mhos cm^{-1}

In Fig. 1, the plot of $1/U_a$ against $1/\sqrt{v}$ has been represented applying the method of least square. The line obeys the equation:

$$1/U_a = 1/U + M/\sqrt{v}$$

FIG. 2

The value of $1/U$ as found from the regression equation ($y = a + bx$, where, a = intercept, b = slope) is 0.4492×10^4 and the slope of the line is 0.1365. The correlation coefficient (r) is 0.5744. Although the value of b is small, statistical t -test reveals that the slope of the line is significantly different from zero. This suggests that a linear regression of y on x may be fitted to the data.

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The value of U , corrected for surface-conductance effect, is 2.23×10^{-4} cm/sec/volt/cm for the particles of Zinc ferrocyanide sol, suspended in a medium of an electrolyte like magnesium sulphate at its equicoagulating concentration.

Again in Fig. 2, is represented the plot of $1/U_a$ against $1/S$ which satisfies the equation

$$1/U_a = 1/U + m/S$$

at the equicoagulating concentrations of the electrolytes used. The linear relationship observed in such cases may be attributed mainly to the effect of surface-conductance, neglecting the ion-relaxation effect as kR is larger than 100 in each case. Alexander and Hunter¹¹ from an analysis of Haydon's data¹² have recently pointed out that the value of visco-electric constant(f) will be about 80 times less than the calculated value (10.2×10^{-10}) used by Lyklema and Overbeek and so the electro-viscous effect will be negligibly small. The value of U as obtained from the intercept on $1/U_a$ axis is 2.25×10^{-4} cm/sec/volt/cm. The two methods thus lead to nearly the same value of U .

TABLE III

Data on sedimentation velocity V and mobility U_a .

(Refer to Fig. 1)

Electrolyte= $MgSO_4$; Sp. conductance at $25^\circ = 0.8139 \times 10^{-3}$ mhos cm^{-1} Conc. of $MgSO_4 = 0.003776(M)$; $pH = 6.50$; Temp. = 25° . Corrected electrophoretic mobility(U) = 2.25×10^{-4} cm/sec/volt/cm.

No. of Obs.	$(\sqrt{v} \times 10^3)$	$10^{-3}/\sqrt{v}$	Obs. electrophoretic mobility (U_a) in cm/sec/volt/cm ($U_a \times 10^4$)	$1/U_a \times 10^{-4}$
1	2.551	0.392	2.000	0.500
2	2.506	0.399	2.000	0.500
3	2.469	0.405	1.953	0.512
4	2.410	0.415	1.961	0.510
5	2.404	0.416	1.988	0.503
6	2.347	0.426	2.016	0.496
7	2.288	0.437	1.969	0.508
8	2.273	0.440	1.969	0.508
9	2.262	0.442	1.992	0.502
10	2.237	0.447	1.923	0.520
11	2.212	0.452	1.953	0.512
12	2.212	0.452	1.923	0.520
13	2.146	0.466	1.957	0.511
14	2.146	0.466	1.961	0.510
15	2.141	0.467	1.959	0.512
16	2.132	0.469	1.908	0.524
17	2.049	0.488	1.961	0.510
18	2.189	0.458	1.998	0.516
19	2.041	0.490	1.953	0.512
20	2.000	0.500	1.988	0.516

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